

Urban Regeneration Strategies of Albanian Industrial Sites

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Abstract

Industrial heritage is representing valuable tangible and intangible resources and characterized by identification processes which must involve different actors and procedures. Their management must be prepared at other scales (local, national and regional), depending on the changes over time so as to promote sustainable development. Today it's a common issue because many world historical properties are excluded from the management system. The main aim of this paper is to identify and study the development of Albanian Industrial Heritage. After the communist period many of the most important industrial sites was in obsolescence, dismantled and neglected for many years. Many of them was destroyed and private warehouses replaced the previous industrial settlements, while others experienced functional transformations either to other industrial uses or to different types. The second aim is to offer evidence, systematize and archive the most important industrial sites in Albania, with a focus on three case studies. The study provides useful information about the history of industrial development and typologies of Albanian industrial buildings and discusses in details the methodologies associated with the reutilization of abandoned industrial sites.

Keywords: Industrial Heritage; Industrial Archaeology; Intangible Asset; Reuse; Revitalization.

1. Introduction

Industrial development in Albania began in the 19th century with the construction of new warehouses equipped with machinery for processing and producing goods such as flour, soap, pasta, and leather. After the Second World War, investments and financial support were provided by former Yugoslavia, Russia, and China, continuing until 1978, when Albania's international relations became restricted [1-4]. Following the regime change in 1990, many state-owned industrial facilities were privatized, while others were abandoned or remained inactive for years. Over time, some privatized sites resumed industrial operations. In addition, both central and local governments have shown growing interest in the reuse and regeneration of these areas, aiming to preserve and highlight their value as part of the country's national heritage [5-8].

In recent years, the re,use of derelict industrial sites presents a growing trend toward an integration of the economic, social and environmental issues. Many of these sites are suitable for strategic intervention through various forms of reuse, such as development of cultural centres, public recreational facilities, new residential areas or mixed-use development schemes [9-13]. These interventions can be important to urban renewal and at the same time they can minimize the risks of land dereliction and metropolitan sprawl. This reconversion process can contribute in substantiating local identity, creating economic opportunities and promoting sustainable urban development in Albania.

2. International Case Studies

2.1 International Methodologies of Industrial Heritage Reuse

The awareness of and protection of industrial heritage in Europe led to the necessity to find ways to promote industrial sites. This led to multiple strategy approaches to their reuse, which generally proved to be successful in economic and social terms. Many countries in Europe faced the problems associated with the decline of industrial regions, pollution, the establishment of new industries unrelated to the existing sites, unawareness of their importance by the public and increasing unemployment. The rejuvenation of unused industrial regions proved to be another argument for establishing better planning systems and law policies in order to improve living standards of the citizens.

Recommendations from ICOMOS and TICCIH regarding the protection and conservation of industrial heritage structures, sites, areas, and landscapes include: ICOMOS [1]:

- a) The development and implementation of appropriate policies, as well as legal and administrative measures, that establish and reflect the relationship between industrial heritage, industrial production, and the economy (including aspects like intellectual property),
- b) Comprehensive inventories and registers of structures, sites, areas, landscapes, their contexts, and related materials like objects, documents, drawings, archives, and intangible heritage should be established and integrated into effective management, conservation, and protection frameworks, ensuring the preservation of their significance, integrity, and authenticity.
- c) In the case of active industrial structures or sites of heritage significance, adequate conditions must be provided for their physical and economic sustainability. Their specific technical characteristics need to be respected while implementing contemporary regulations.
- d) Since functional integrity is essential to the significance of industrial heritage structures and sites, appropriate protection measures should be enforced. The overall heritage value of these assets can either increase or diminish depending on whether key components are preserved or removed.

As authors discuss [2], policies that can emerge to achieve economic development strategies are as follows:

- a) Import substitution strategies can be encouraged by creating locally distinctive markets that offer goods and experiences not readily available elsewhere.
- b) Modernization efforts should prioritize improved comfort and safety while safeguarding the integrity of historic assets.
- c) Heritage buildings can be effectively repurposed as venues for artistic and cultural activities.
- d) Historic structures are often adapted into economically viable spaces that generate new forms of revenue.
- e) The adaptive reuse of heritage sites represents a mutually beneficial approach for cities, especially when diverse functions and activities are introduced.
- f) The development of historic sites can serve as a strategic tool applicable across different global contexts.
- g) Both small- and large-scale revitalization projects can be implemented in alignment with public interests and available resources.
- h) Conservation and regeneration initiatives can be pursued not only during periods of economic growth but also in times of decline, contributing to employment and local income generation.
- i) Heritage revitalization operates as a cumulative strategy, producing impacts that extend beyond local communities to the broader urban context.
- j) The involvement of non-governmental organizations can play a crucial role in revitalization processes by facilitating collaboration between civil society and policymakers.
- k) Heritage conservation offers a pathway to modernization while preserving local identity and distinctiveness.
- l) Economic benefits are closely linked to uniqueness, diversity, and identity—qualities that are inherent in protected heritage sites.

Recommendations from the regional policy imply as follows, as discussed by the Directorate-General for Internal Policies [3]:

- a) European level: Industrial policy at the European level should support international competitiveness and growth. In parallel, Cohesion policy should assist cities and regions to find pathways to industrial development and regeneration.
- b) Member state level: National industrial policies need to ensure resilience in the face of further potential crises by enabling cities and regions to develop diversified economic structures, notably through horizontal policy measures. This is especially important in Convergence countries, where Cohesion policy co-funds national industrial and economic development policies.
- c) Local and regional level: Strategies for cities and regions, especially those with a historic legacy of old industries, need to promote diversified development, without over-fragmenting policy goals and investment. A narrow focus on individual industries (or one or two clusters) risks nourishing the declining areas

of tomorrow. Cohesion policy programme strategies should reflect the need to build resilience against a crisis.

Lastly, an interesting concept is the energy benefits of recycling buildings, lately discussed by Watson⁶. The performance of adapted buildings should be improved in order to attain energy savings. Best practices that could be mentioned are Tower Mills in Stawick, Scotland, and Finlayson Mill, Finland.

2.2 International case studies of industrial heritage sites rehabilitation

Today, many prominent examples of industrial tourism can be identified worldwide. Among them can be mentioned best practices in Wolfsburg, where the focus is on the Volkswagen site; in Cologne, where a wide array of different types of industries are included; in the Pays de la Loire region namely the Nantes and Saint Nazaire areas; in Turin, whose industrial history was linked to the Fiat site; in Rotterdam, which excels for its port/industrial infrastructure. These cases present examples of repurposing industrial heritage into tourism attractions.

2.1.1 Montemartini Power Station, Roma Ostiense, Italy

The ex-Therma Electrical Station Giovanni Montemartini is located in the oldest industrialized area of Rome. Constructed in 1912, it was the first public power station in the city, using some of the most modern machinery of the time. It was functional since 1963, when part of the implant started to decay and for the next twenty years it was not in working conditions. In 1980, the Municipal Water and Electricity Company organized a partial restoration of the area and old machinery, transforming it into a museum. Later on, in 1997, an exhibition of Roman sculptures temporary transferred from the Capitolini Museum, which was being restructured. The success of the exhibition led to the announcement of this museum as a house for permanent art exposition. Actually, the museum offers an interesting itinerary, passing through art sculptures, old power station machinery, and work tools. The internal structure of buildings and machinery of the old central station is intentionally left visible (Figure 1).

Figure 1. (a) - Montemartini Central, 1924 [12] (b) - Machineries hall [8]

The regeneration project has emphasized the unique values of heritage, reflecting the industrial past and technological developments of the country. Becoming the shipyard of Roman Industrial Archaeology, this industrial forum is recognized as cultural heritage, as described by Fiore [4]. The following (Figure 2) illustrates the urban change of the Montemartini site during two decades.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2. Montemartini Central (Google Earth (a)-1943 vs. (b)-2026)

Montemartini Museum is a successful case of great synthesis between ancient, industrial, and modern ages. The project itself is part of the urban requalification of the oldest industrial area of Rome (including the Slaughterhouse, the Gasometer, port facilities, the former Mira Lanza, and the old General Markets), also with the arrangement of university buildings and the construction of Science City.

2.1.2 Vitkovice Ironworks, Ostrava, in the Czech Republic

Ostrava is among the largest urban areas in the country. It is renowned, among else, for the existence of educational institutions, art galleries and museums, recreational facilities and the scope of cultural events. The first coal mines were established here during the 18th century, leading to the further development of the region, with the creation of ironworks and further coal mines. The most significant was the Vítkovice Ironworks, regarded as the “steel centre of the country”. This consisted of the blast furnaces, colliery, chemical plant, train line, coking plant and the power station.

The site ceased operations in 1998 due to economic restructuring and successive industrial closures. Over time, the area deteriorated, and many of its structures fell into disrepair. Although the complex was designated as a Cultural Monument in 2000 and later as a National Cultural Monument in 2002, it was not until 2008 that a comprehensive redevelopment project was approved, including its recognition within European heritage frameworks. The regeneration initiative focused on preserving key historic elements while adapting the site for new uses, such as a university campus, commercial activities, housing, and cultural functions. With an investment of approximately €37 million largely led by Josef Pleskot and funded by the European Union, the Czech Republic, Vítkovice a.s., and the Lower Vítkovice Area Association, the complex has been successfully revitalized. Today, the Vítkovice Ironworks is part of the European Route of Industrial Heritage.

The regeneration project included: conversion of an old gas holder into a congress centre, empowerment station into education and university centre (the World of Technology), blast furnace into sightseeing tower, extension of streets and construction of a new building (Big World of Technology) accommodating lecture, laboratories and exhibition spaces (Figure 3). On the other side, the process was also associated with some significant obstacles regarding property rights (ownership may not be clear as they change often, or is not clear) and environmental pollution levels, as by Klempa [5].

The singularity of the long, continuous industrial complex has become a symbol of the city’s skyline (Figure 4). It embodies a successful combination of old monuments with revitalized buildings and prevents further degradation. “It shows that industrial sites can be utilized for the benefit of the public and the city as a space for culture, education, and leisure. Using this space for the development of culture and education has proved benefits in many ways, as described by [6].

Figure 3. Vitkovice Ironworks [7]

Figure 4. Ostrava Industrial Site Skyline [13]

Additionally, the Vitkovice Ironworks site transformations during the last decade (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Vitkovice, Ironworks (Google Earth, 2006 vs. 2026).

3. Albanian Case Studies

The history and evolution of the industry and the Albanian is constantly linked to the historical, political, and social context of the entire nation. The first investments in the sector were made in the second half of the 19th century to the fall of the communist regime (1991); they were almost always related to political alliances with foreign states. An interpretation of the Albanian history of industrialization has been conceptualized in the following graphic, see Figure 6.

Figure 6. History of industrialization in Albania [Elaborated by the author].

The following is a list of industrial sites constructed during industrialization in Albania, since 1914, explaining the distribution of these industries all over the country.

Table 1. Industrial sites in Albania of the highest interest (Elaborated by author).

City	Name of object	Type of industry	Year of construction	Description of activity
Berat	Textile Combine “Mao Ce Dun”	Light and Industry	1966-1970	Textile implant
Elbasan	Metallurgical Combine “The Steal of Party”	Heavy	1966-1970	Metallurgical complex (520 buildings)
Fier	Thermal Power Plant (TEC)	Energy	1966	Thermal Power Plant
Kuçova	Mechanical Oil Plant (UMN)	Heavy	1934	The bitumen barrels, the motors V2-300, the piston, and the probes were produced
Laç	Superphosphate factory	Heavy	1966-1970	It was the first and the only one in Albania
Tirana	Textile Combine “Stalin”	Light and Food	1951-1955	Construction started with the ex-BRSS investment and then passed by the Chinese

Figures 7 until 9 depict some important photos from main cities such as Elbasan, Kuçova and Laç

Figure 7. “Steel of Party” – Metallurgical Complex of Elbasan (Photo by the author).

Figure 8. TEC, Kuçova (Photo by the author).

Figure 9. Superphosphate Complex, Laç (Photo by the author).

The ongoing table illustrates the overall regeneration model proposed, describing possible regeneration model proposed by the authors.

Table 2. Albanian industrial case studies, regeneration proposals.

Category	Elbasan	Kuçova	Laç
Economic & urban development	Diversification, logistics, incubators	Tourism regeneration	Green protection, regeneration
Environment	Environmental analysis	Waste treatment	Soil remediation
Heritage	Branding & community	Reuse oil structures	Tourism identity

4. Summary and Conclusion

Industrial heritage exists in nearly every city in Albania, some of which (mainly large metallurgical and mechanical plants) are significant indicators of a major epoch in the country's industrialization. Some of them previously formed an important part of the urban fabric, but a rapid urban growth process and extension of the housing areas have transformed them into underused "brown-field sites". Over a period exceeding 20 years of economic liberalisation, the urban processes of a number of towns have marginalized in some cases these brown field sites. With the General National Plan and the General Local Plans being in process of getting approval, increasing attention is paid to the insertion of the underutilized industrial sites from "dead" to "live" assets as part of the urban, economic, social, cultural and environmental fabric of the cities, with resulting benefits for local communities.

Reuse of industrial heritage can pass through the following models:

- i. No intervention, which mostly ends in heritage degradation.
- ii. Conservative intervention
- iii. Interventions in façade – wall insulation, change of windows
- iv. Interventions in interior:
 - Add vertical space divisions
 - Add horizontal space, divisions
 - Create inner courts
 - Construct a new roof
 - Passive design as natural ventilation (ventilated halls can increase the aesthetics of interior), natural lighting (reorganize interior functions to make possible natural lighting when needed), alternative energy sources (geothermal energy, photovoltaic panel), and water reutilization (for internal and external purposes).
- v. Interventions in the interior and exterior of buildings and urban renewal (could even provide a self-sustainable ecosystem):
 - Improvement of infrastructure (accessibility, water supply and reuse, electricity, heating and cooling systems, drainage)

- Ecological measures (soil, water, air purification)
 - Vivid and save public spaces
 - Landscape protection (combination of heritage buildings with the surrounding environment, sustainable development)
- vi. Destruction of old remains and construction of new facilities – this is usually applied in cases of urban renewal, when existing structures are in very bad condition, and the process passes through the destruction of old buildings and site cleaning.

Determining the most appropriate method of intervention is a complex and multifaceted process. The strategies implemented can help reduce urban pressures, enhance environmental quality, attract both local and international investment, promote the sustainable use of buildings, and improve overall energy efficiency.

Based on the international case studies examined in the third chapter, most large-scale industrial sites particularly those related to heavy, energy, or mechanical industries—have been repurposed into spaces dedicated to art, culture, education, sports, leisure, museums, residential use, or creative industries. Only a limited number have been redeveloped as business parks or logistics centres. This suggests that expansive industrial buildings are especially well suited for transformation into facilities that support cultural, educational, and recreational activities. Drawing on these international experiences, the Albanian case studies could address existing urban needs by providing more public recreational spaces, improving residential environments, and fostering creative and economic opportunities for local communities.

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